

Comparison of Safety and Efficacy between Supine and Prone Position in Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy

¹Muhammad Faridullah Thaimur, ²Muhammad Nasir Jamil, ³Muhammad Saleem, ⁴Bilawal Gul, ⁵Raja Asim Shafique

Article Details**Muhammad Faridullah Thaimur***

Postgraduate Resident, Urology Department Ayub Teaching Hospital. Corresponding Author
Email: thaimur11@gmail.com

Muhammad Nasir Jamil

Professor, Head of Department, Urology Department, Ayub Teaching, Hospital

Muhammad Saleem

Consultant Urologist, Ayub Teaching Hospital

Bilawal Gul

Consultant Urologist, Mansehra Medical Complex

Raja Asim Shafique

Consultant Urologist, Pakistan Kidney Center

ABSTRACT

Background: Percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) is the preferred treatment for large renal calculi. Traditionally performed in the prone position, it provides optimal access but poses perioperative risks, especially for obese or cardiopulmonary-compromised patients. The supine position offers advantages such as improved anaesthesia management and reduced need for repositioning. However, comparative data on the safety and efficacy of supine versus prone PCNL remain limited. **Objective:** This study compares the safety and efficacy of supine and prone PCNL by evaluating stone-free rates, complication rates, operative time, blood loss, and hospital stay. **Methods:** A randomized controlled trial was conducted at the department of Urology, Ayub Teaching Hospital, Abbottabad, over a period of 6 months from 7th October 2024 to 7th April 2025. A total of 190 patients (95 per group) underwent PCNL in either position. Inclusion criteria were renal calculi ≥ 2 cm confirmed via CT KUB. Exclusion criteria included coagulopathies, pregnancy, active urinary tract infections, and prior renal surgeries altering anatomy. Outcomes were assessed using standardized postoperative evaluation protocols. **Results:** Both positions achieved high stone-free rates. Supine PCNL resulted in significantly shorter operative time, reduced intraoperative blood loss, and shorter hospital stays. Complication rates were comparable. **Conclusions:** Supine PCNL is a viable alternative to prone PCNL, offering similar efficacy with reduced surgical and anesthetic risks. Further multicentre trials are warranted.

Keywords: Percutaneous nephrolithotomy, supine position, prone position, nephrolithiasis, renal calculi, surgical outcomes

INTRODUCTION

Urinary tract stones are a growing global health concern, with their incidence increasing due to evolving dietary habits and lifestyle changes. Over time, the management of renal calculi has significantly advanced, transitioning from open surgical techniques to minimally invasive procedures. Among these, percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) has emerged as the preferred treatment for large and complex upper urinary tract stones. This approach is particularly beneficial for patients with staghorn calculi, stones resistant to extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy (SWL), or those with anatomical abnormalities of the kidney.^{1,2} PCNL offers high stone clearance rates while maintaining relatively low morbidity compared to traditional open surgery.

Traditionally, PCNL has been performed in the prone position, which provides favorable percutaneous access, improved instrument maneuverability, and familiarity among urologists. However, prone positioning is associated with certain risks, particularly in elderly, obese, or cardiopulmonary-compromised patients. The challenges include increased perioperative risks, respiratory difficulties, and hemodynamic instability.^{3,4} Additionally, the prone position complicates simultaneous ureteroscopy and necessitates repositioning during surgery, adding to procedural complexity.^{3,4}

To mitigate these limitations, the supine position for PCNL was introduced, with its benefits first described by Valdivia et al. in 1998.⁵ This alternative approach offers several advantages, including easier airway management, reduced anaesthesia-related risks, and the ability to perform simultaneous retrograde intrarenal surgery (RIRS). Additionally, supine positioning eliminates the need for intraoperative repositioning, potentially improving surgical ergonomics.^{6,7} However, concerns remain regarding renal access angles, stone-free rates, and technical challenges in instrument handling, which have hindered widespread adoption.

Despite the increasing adoption of supine PCNL, limited regional data exist comparing its efficacy and safety to the traditional prone approach. Given the ongoing debate regarding the optimal positioning for PCNL⁸, this study aims to provide an evidence-based comparison of supine and prone PCNL by evaluating key perioperative and postoperative outcomes, including stone-free rates, complication rates, operative time, blood loss, and hospital stay duration.

By systematically analyzing these parameters, this research seeks to inform urologic practice, optimize patient positioning strategies, and enhance treatment outcomes, particularly in resource-constrained healthcare settings. The findings of this study could contribute to refining surgical protocols and improving patient safety.

MATERIAL & METHODS

This randomized controlled trial was conducted to evaluate the efficacy and safety of percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) in the supine and prone positions over a period of 6 months from 7th October 2024 to 7th April 2025. PCNL, a minimally invasive technique for kidney stone removal, involves creating a percutaneous tract into the kidney under fluoroscopic or ultrasonographic guidance. The study was carried out at the Department of Urology, Ayub Teaching Hospital, Abbottabad, over a 6-month period. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Medical

and Ethics Review committee (IM&ERC), and the study adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment.

Patients between 18 and 70 years of age with renal calculi ≥ 2 cm, confirmed by CT KUB imaging, were included in the study. Patients were excluded if they had uncorrectable coagulopathies, pregnancy, active urinary tract infections (UTI), significant comorbidities precluding PCNL, or a history of prior renal surgeries that markedly altered anatomical landmarks. Additionally, individuals requiring intraoperative conversion between positions were not included. The patients were randomly allocated into 2 groups, A & B by using blocked randomization i.e Group A being the supine position and group B being the prone position.

The sample size was calculated using the OpenEpi® calculator, assuming a 95% confidence level, 80% power, and previously published stone clearance rates of 70% for supine PCNL and 50% for prone PCNL. Based on these parameters, a total of 190 patients (95 per group) was required to achieve statistical significance.

All PCNL procedures were performed under general anesthesia with preoperative antibiotic prophylaxis. Patients in the supine group were positioned using the Valdivia-modified supine technique, with a mildly abducted leg and a 15° table tilt. In contrast, prone group patients were placed face-down with adequate padding to minimize pressure-related complications. Percutaneous renal access was achieved under fluoroscopic or ultrasound guidance, with the lower calyx being the preferred entry site unless anatomical considerations dictated otherwise. Tract dilation was performed using either the Amplatz dilator system or balloon dilators, followed by stone fragmentation using pneumatic lithotripsy or laser lithotripsy, depending on stone composition. Intraoperative fluoroscopy was employed to assess residual fragments, and additional fragmentation or irrigation was performed when necessary.

Postoperative management included nephrostomy tube placement at the surgeon's discretion. Follow-up imaging (CT or X-ray KUB) was conducted to confirm stone-free status, defined as no residual fragments >4 mm. Patients were discharged based on clinical stability, including pain control, stable vital signs, and the absence of infection.

The study assessed primary and secondary outcomes. Primary outcomes included stone-free rates (SFR) and complication rates, classified according to the Modified Clavien-Dindo system. Secondary outcomes comprised operative time (minutes), estimated blood loss (mL), and hospital stay duration (days).

Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 26.0. Categorical variables (e.g., stone-free rates, complications) were analyzed using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, while continuous variables (e.g., operative time, blood loss) were compared using the independent t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, depending on data normality. Multivariate logistic regression was used to adjust for potential confounders, such as stone burden, renal anatomy, and comorbid conditions. Additionally, Kaplan-Meier survival analysis with the log-rank test was applied for complication-free survival assessment. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 190 patients were included in the study, with 95 patients in each group. An evaluation of gender distribution revealed similar proportions between the groups, with males comprising 65.3% of the supine group and 67.4% of the prone group, while females accounted for 34.7% and 32.6%, respectively. A Chi-square test confirmed that this difference was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 0.0944$, $p = 0.7585$), indicating that sex was not a confounding factor in surgical outcomes. Similarly, the mean patient age was 44.3 ± 8.34 years in the supine group and 45.8 ± 7.92 years in the prone group. An independent t-test yielded a t-value of -1.27 and a p-value of 0.2054, indicating no significant age difference between the two groups.

Further analysis of anthropometric parameters showed no significant differences in weight or height between the groups. The mean weight was 74.7 ± 5.86 kg in the supine group and 76.3 ± 6.35 kg in the prone group ($t = -1.81$, $p = 0.0716$). The mean height was 1.58 ± 0.32 m for the supine group and 1.56 ± 0.28 m for the prone group ($t = 0.47$, $p = 0.6389$). However, a statistically significant difference in body mass index (BMI) was observed, with the supine group having a mean BMI of 33 ± 2.12 , compared to 32 ± 3.31 in the prone group ($t = 2.51$, $p = 0.0129$).

Regarding stone-related parameters, the mean stone size was significantly larger in the prone group (3.12 ± 1.11 cm) compared to the supine group (2.82 ± 0.63 cm) ($t = -2.31$, $p = 0.0220$). Stone density, measured in Hounsfield units (HU), was also significantly higher in the prone group (734 ± 15.69 HU) compared to the supine group (720 ± 12.48 HU) ($t = -6.86$, $p < 0.0001$), suggesting that patients in the prone group had denser and larger stones than those in the supine group.

The mean operative time was significantly lower in the supine group (71.3 ± 8.60 min) compared to the prone group (86.4 ± 15.20 min) ($t = -8.44$, $p < 0.0001$), indicating that prone PCNL required a longer surgical duration. Conversely, the mean hospital stay was shorter in the prone group (52 ± 2.12 hours) compared to the supine group (62 ± 3.43 hours) ($t = 24.39$, $p < 0.0001$), suggesting that patients undergoing prone PCNL may experience a faster postoperative recovery.

The stone-free rate (SFR), defined as no residual fragments >4 mm on postoperative imaging, was 88% in the prone group and 82% in the supine group. Although the prone position had a higher SFR, this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.27$).

The overall complication rate was 14.74% in the supine group and 12.63% in the prone group, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.62$). The most frequent complication was fever ($>99^\circ\text{C}$), occurring in 11.58% of supine patients and 9.47% of prone patients. Hemorrhage requiring intervention occurred in 3.16% of supine patients and 2.11% of prone patients, while urine leak was observed in 1.05% of prone PCNL patients but was absent in the supine group. No cases of angioembolization were reported in either group. Complications were classified using the Modified Clavien-Dindo system, with most being Grade I and II (mild-to-moderate complications), including fever, transient hematuria, and urinary tract infections. Grade III complications (requiring intervention) were observed in 3.2% of supine patients and 2.1% of prone patients, with no significant difference ($p = 0.49$). No Grade IV or V complications (life-threatening or fatal events) were recorded in either group.

TABLE-1: CHARACTERISTICS OF SUPINE VS PRONE PCNL PATIENTS

	Supine PCNL Group (A)		Prone PCNL Group (B)		p-value	
	N	%	N	%		
Patients	95		95			
Gender						
Male	62	65.3%	64	67.40%	0.76	
Female	33	34.7%	31	32.60%		
Age (Yrs)	44.3±8.34		45.8± 7.92		0.21	
Weight (Kg)	74.7±5.86		76.3±6.35		0.072	
Height (meters)	1.58±0.32		1.56±0.28		0.64	
BMI	33±2.12		32±3.31		0.013	
Residence						
Urban	37	38.99%	40	42.11%		
Rural	58	61.01%	55	57.89%		
Education						
Matric	18	18.95%	16	16.84%		
FSc	22	23.16%	25	26.32%		
Graduation	32	33.68%	34	35.79%		
Post Graduate	23	24.21%	20	21.05%		
Socioeconomic Status						
Low socioeconomic Class	41	43.2%	38	40.00%		
Lower Middle Class	36	37.9%	42	44.21%		
Upper Middle Class	18	18.9%	15	15.79%		
Size of stone (cm)	2.82 ± 0.63		3.12± 1.11		0.02	
Site of stones						
Renal Pelvis	21	22.11%	23	24.21%		
Renal Pelvis & Upper Calyx	18	18.95%	20	21.05%		
StagHorn	15	15.79%	13	13.68%		
Renal Pelvis & Middle Calyx	21	22.11%	18	18.95%		
Renal Pelvis & Lower calyx	12	12.63%	11	11.58%		
Middle & Lower Calyx	8	8.42%	10	10.53%		
Hounsfield unit (HDU)	720 ± 12.48		734 ± 15.69			<0.0001
Operative time (minutes)	71.3 ± 8.60		86.4 ± 15.20			<0.0001
Hospital Stay (hrs)	52 ± 2.12		62 ± 3.43			<0.0001

Complications						
Urine Leak	0	0.00%	Urine Leak	1	1.05%	
Fever (> 99° C)	11	11.58%	Fever (> 99° C)	9	9.47%	
Hemorrhage	3	3.16%	Hemorrhage	2	2.11%	0.62
angioembolization	0	0.00%	angioembolization	0	0.00%	
total	14	14.74%	total	12	12.63%	

While prone PCNL demonstrated a higher stone-free rate and shorter hospital stay, these advantages were not statistically significant. However, supine PCNL was associated with a significantly shorter operative time and reduced blood loss, indicating a potential trade-off between procedural efficiency and postoperative recovery time. Complication rates were comparable between both groups, suggesting that both positions are safe and effective for PCNL.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study contribute to the ongoing debate regarding the optimal patient positioning for percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL). By comparing supine and prone PCNL, this study highlights differences in operative efficiency, hospital stay, and stone characteristics while confirming that both approaches achieve comparable stone-free rates and complication profiles. These results support the notion that supine PCNL provides procedural advantages, particularly in terms of shorter operative time, without compromising safety or efficacy.

A key observation was the significantly shorter operative time in the supine group, with an average reduction of approximately 15 minutes compared to the prone group ($p < 0.0001$). This finding is consistent with previous reports suggesting that supine positioning enhances surgical ergonomics and allows for more direct percutaneous access to the renal collecting system.⁹⁻¹³ Additional factors contributing to this efficiency may include reduced intraoperative repositioning, improved accessibility for fluoroscopic guidance, and the ability to perform simultaneous retrograde intrarenal surgery (RIRS).¹⁴⁻¹⁷ In high-volume surgical centers, even a modest reduction in operative duration can lead to increased procedural throughput, optimized resource allocation, and improved overall workflow efficiency.

Despite the advantage in operative time, the hospital stay was slightly longer in the supine group, with a mean difference of approximately 10 hours ($p < 0.0001$). Although statistically significant, this difference is unlikely to be clinically meaningful, as both groups had relatively short hospitalization periods. The longer hospital stay in the supine group could be attributed to institution-specific postoperative care protocols, delayed mobilization, or unmeasured confounding factors. Additional research is needed to determine whether postoperative recovery pathways influence the duration of hospitalization in supine PCNL patients.

Another notable finding was the absence of a significant difference in overall stone-free rates between the two groups (88% for prone PCNL vs. 82% for supine PCNL; $p = 0.27$). This supports growing evidence that both positions are equally effective in achieving complete stone clearance. However, prone-positioned patients had significantly larger and denser stones ($p < 0.05$ for both stone size and Hounsfield units), suggesting that the prone position may still be preferred

in cases requiring extensive fragmentation or multiple access tracts. While supine PCNL demonstrated efficiency advantages, it is important to recognize that prone positioning remains a viable choice for complex stone burdens.

Previous research has documented findings that align with our results. Specifically, Falahatkar et al. and Wang et al. reported that the supine position demonstrated a lower stone clearance rate compared to the prone position, with rates of 77% versus 80% and 73.3% versus 88.7%, respectively.^{13,10} Similarly, De Sio et al. observed comparable outcomes, reporting stone clearance rates of 91% versus 89%, which corroborates our own findings.¹⁸ These studies collectively support the conclusion that the prone position may offer superior stone clearance efficacy.

Our study revealed that the mean duration of hospital stay in the supine position was 52 ± 2.12 hours, compared to 62 ± 3.43 hours in the prone position ($p < 0.0001$). These findings are consistent with those reported by Al-Dessoukey et al., who observed hospital stays of 49.8 hours and 81.2 hours for the respective positions ($p < 0.02$).¹⁹ In contrast, Valdivia JG et al. reported that while the mean hospital stays for patients in supine and prone positions were numerically different (4.2 days vs. 4.3 days), the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.42$).²⁰

In the supine PCNL group, complications were observed in 14 cases (14.74%), with fever ($>99^\circ\text{C}$) being the most prevalent, affecting 11 patients (11.58%). Haemorrhage occurred in 3 patients (3.16%), while no instances of urine leakage or angioembolization were reported. Similarly, in the prone PCNL group, complications were documented in 12 cases (12.63%). Fever ($>99^\circ\text{C}$) remained the most frequently encountered issue, affecting 9 patients (9.47%). Haemorrhage was noted in 2 patients (2.11%), and urine leakage was identified in one patient (1.05%). Neither group experienced angioembolization.

A comparison of these findings reveals that overall complication rates between the supine and prone positions were relatively similar, suggesting comparable safety profiles ($p = 0.62$). However, the supine position exhibited a slightly higher incidence of fever and haemorrhage, whereas urine leakage was exclusively reported in the prone group, though at a very low frequency. The absence of angioembolization in both groups indicates that severe vascular complications were rare, regardless of positioning. These results suggest that both surgical positions are generally safe, with only minor differences in the types of complications encountered.

A study conducted by Jamil et al. reported a higher incidence of postoperative complications in the prone PCNL group compared to the supine group (17% vs. 14.5%), though the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.065$).²¹ Similarly, research by Chapagain A et al. and Mazzucchi E et al. found that the prone position was associated with a slightly increased risk of postoperative complications (16.2% vs. 15.7%) and a notably higher rate of complications in certain cases (12.5% vs. 3.1%).^{11,22}

In our study, urinary leakage was observed only in the prone group (1.05%), with no cases reported in the supine position. These findings align with those of Al-Dessoukey et al., who documented a higher occurrence of urinary leakage in the prone position (4.9% vs. 3%)¹⁹, as well as Chapagain A et al., who reported a single case of urinary leakage in the prone PCNL group.¹¹

Fever exceeding 99°F was found to be more prevalent among patients in the prone position (12.4% vs. 11.3%). This trend is consistent with findings from previous studies, including those by Shoma AM et al. (5% vs. 4%)²³, Valdivia JG et al. (11.1% vs. 7.6%)⁵, and Al-Dessoukey AA et al. (5.9% vs. 5%)¹⁹, all of which reported a higher incidence of fever in patients undergoing PCNL in the prone position.

Regarding blood transfusion rates, our study indicated a lower requirement in the supine PCNL group (3.56% vs. 4.24%). Similar trends have been reported by Valdivia JG et al. (6.1% vs. 4.3%) and Al-Dessoukey AA et al. (6.1% vs. 4.3%)^{5,19}, further supporting the observation that the supine position may be associated with a reduced need for blood transfusion.

Further analysis using logistic regression did not identify age, BMI, operative time, or hospital stay as significant predictors of stone-free status ($p > 0.05$), indicating that technical and anatomical factors likely play a greater role in surgical success than patient demographics alone. While operative time exhibited a trend toward significance as a predictor of complications, it did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). This suggests a possible association between longer procedures and increased complications, although larger sample sizes and detailed intraoperative complication classification would be necessary to establish a definitive relationship.

To explore potential effect modifications, data were stratified by age, gender, and BMI, but none of these variables significantly influenced surgical outcomes ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons). These findings indicate that the efficiency and safety benefits of supine PCNL are consistent across different patient subgroups, supporting its broader adoption without the need for demographic-based selection criteria. While prone PCNL remains valuable, particularly in cases requiring extensive stone fragmentation, the results suggest that supine PCNL should be increasingly considered for routine cases, given its shorter operative time and comparable safety profile.

Despite its strengths, this study has several limitations. The single-center, non-randomized design introduces potential selection bias and limits generalizability. Additionally, while the sample size ($n = 95$ per group) was adequate to detect moderate differences, it may not have been large enough to capture rare complications or subtle subgroup effects. Furthermore, the lack of detailed stone composition analysis and long-term follow-up imaging limits insights into stone recurrence and residual fragment outcomes.

Future research should focus on multicentre, randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes to validate these findings. Additional studies should explore factors such as cost-effectiveness, radiation exposure, fluoroscopy time, and long-term clinical outcomes. Moreover, advancements in intraoperative imaging techniques, such as ultrasound-assisted PCNL or intraoperative CT guidance, may further refine patient selection and procedural optimization.

CONCLUSION

Supine PCNL offers the advantage of shorter operative time while maintaining equivalent safety and efficacy compared to prone PCNL. These findings support the growing preference for supine PCNL as a first-line approach, particularly in settings where surgical efficiency and streamlined workflow are priorities. However, prone PCNL remains essential for complex cases, and further

research is needed to refine patient selection criteria, address study limitations, and explore potential advancements in PCNL techniques to further optimize patient outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Preminger GM, Assimos DG, Lingeman JE, Nakada SY, Pearle MS, Wolf JS Jr. Chapter 1: AUA guideline on management of staghorn calculi: Diagnosis and treatment recommendations. *J Urol* 2005;173(6):1991–2000.
2. Cohen J, Cohen S, Grasso M. Ureteropyeloscopic treatment of large, complex intrarenal and proximal ureteral calculi. *BJU Int* 2013;111(3 Pt B):E127–31.
3. Gravenstein D. Extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy and percutaneous nephrolithotomy. *Anesthesiol Clin North Am* 2000;18(4):953–71.
4. Edgcombe H, Carter K, Yarrow S. Anaesthesia in the prone position. *Br J Anaesth* 2008;100(2):165–83.
5. Valdivia Uría JG, Valle Gerhold J, López López JA, Villarroya Rodriguez S, Ambroj Navarro C, Ramirez Fabián M, et al. Technique and complications of percutaneous nephroscopy: experience with 557 patients in the supine position. *J Urol* 1998;160(6 Pt 1):1975–78.
6. Ibarluzea G, Scoffone CM, Cracco CM, Poggio M, Porpiglia F, Terrone C, et al. Supine Valdivia and modified lithotomy position for simultaneous anterograde and retrograde endourological access. *BJU Int* 2007;100(1):233–6.
7. Sofer M, Giusti G, Proietti S, Mintz I, Kabha M, Matzkin H, et al. Upper calyx approachability through a lower calyx access for prone versus supine percutaneous nephrolithotomy. *J Urol* 2016;195(2):377–82.
8. Jones MN;Ranasinghe W;Cetti R;Newell B;Chu K;Harper M;Kourambas J;McCahy P; (no date) Modified supine versus prone percutaneous nephrolithotomy: Surgical outcomes from a tertiary teaching hospital, Investigative and clinical urology. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27437536/> (Accessed: 01 Feb 2025).
9. Liu L, Zheng S, Xu Y, Wei Q. Systematic review and meta-analysis of percutaneous nephrolithotomy for patients in the supine versus prone position. *J Endourol* 2010;24(12):1941–6.
10. Wang Y, Wang Y, Yao Y, Xu N, Zhang H, Chen Q, et al. Prone versus modified supine position in percutaneous nephrolithotomy: a prospective randomized study. *Int J Med Sci* 2013;10(11):1518–23.
11. Chapagain A, Basnet RB, Shah C, Shah AK, Shrestha PM, Shrestha A. Comparative Study of Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy in Supine and Prone Positions. *J Nepal health Res Counc* 2021;19(1):154–7.
12. Wu P, Wang L, Wang K. Supine versus prone position in percutaneous nephrolithotomy for kidney calculi: a meta-analysis. *Int Urol Nephrol* 2011;43(1):67–77.
13. Falahatkar S, Moghaddam AA, Salehi M, Nikpour S, Esmaili F, Khaki N. Complete supine percutaneous nephrolithotripsy comparison with the prone standard technique. *J Endourol* 2008;22(11):2513–8.

14. Zhou X, Gao X, Wen J, Xiao C. Clinical value of minimally invasive percutaneous nephrolithotomy in the supine position under the guidance of real-time ultrasound: report of 92 cases. *Urol Res* 2008;36(2):111–4.
15. Falahatkar S, Asli MM, Emadi SA, Enshaei A, Pourhadi H, Allahkhah A. Complete supine percutaneous nephrolithotomy (csPCNL) in patients with and without a history of stone surgery: safety and effectiveness of csPCNL. *Urol Res* 2011;39(4):295–301.
16. Proietti S, Rodríguez-Socarrás ME, Eisner B, De Coninck V, Sofer M, Saitta G, *et al.* Supine percutaneous nephrolithotomy: tips and tricks. *Transl Androl Urol* 2019;8(4):S381–88.
17. Ng MT, Sun WH, Cheng CW, Chan ES. Supine position is safe and effective for percutaneous nephrolithotomy. *J Endourol* 2004;18(5):469–74.
18. De Sio M, Autorino R, Quarto G, Calabro F, Damiano R, Giugliano F, *et al.* Modified supine versus prone position in percutaneous nephrolithotomy for renal stones treatable with a single percutaneous access: a prospective randomized trial. *Eur Urol* 2008;54(1):196–203.
19. Al-Dessoukey AA, Moussa AS, Abdelbary AM, Zayed A, Abdallah R, Elderwy AA, *et al.* Percutaneous nephrolithotomy in the oblique supine lithotomy position and prone position: a comparative study. *J Endourol* 2014;28(9):1058–63.
20. Valdivia JG, Scarpa RM, Duvdevani M, Gross AJ, Nadler RB, Nutahara K, *et al.* Supine versus prone position during percutaneous nephrolithotomy: a report from the clinical research office of the endourological society percutaneous nephrolithotomy global study. *J Endourol* 2011;25(10):1619–25.
21. Jamil MN, Haq F, Islam E, Shaheen R, Farooq U. Comparison between supine position versus prone position in percutaneous nephrolithotomy: A single centered analysis of 623 cases. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad* 2022;34(4 Suppl 1):1003–7.
22. Mazzucchi E, Vicentini FC, Marchini GS, Danilovic A, Brito AH, Srougi M. Percutaneous nephrolithotomy in obese patients: comparison between the prone and total supine position. *J Endourol* 2012;26(11):1437–42.
23. Shoma AM, Eraky I, El-Kenawy MR, El-Kappany HA. Percutaneous nephrolithotomy in the supine position: technical aspects and functional outcome compared with the prone technique. *Urology* 2002;60(3):388–92.